

1 Proposing a circular economy for mine tailings: using them as catalysts in the
2 treatment of landfill leachate

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13 Abstract

14 Mine tailings (MT), a significant by-product of the mining industry, pose
15 environmental risks due to their metal content and social hazards when they are
16 located near urban areas. However, their mineral composition, rich in feldspars,
17 quartz, phyllosilicates, and TiO₂, offers potential for reuse within a circular economy
18 framework. In this context, this study evaluates the catalytic application of MT in a
19 sonophotocatalytic process to treat mature landfill leachate (LL), a recalcitrant
20 effluent with low biodegradability. Using a full factorial design, the effects of catalyst
21 load, hydrogen peroxide concentration, and pH of the solution on the removal of total
22 organic carbon (TOC), Chemical Oxygen Demand and aromatic compounds
23 (Abs₂₅₄) of the landfill leachate were assessed. Optimal conditions (2000 mg/L MT,
24 3000 mg/L H₂O₂, pH 3) led to 29.8% and 50.2% removal of TOC and aromatic
25 compounds, respectively. Under these optimized physicochemical conditions
26 applied for 3 hours of treatment, the removal of TOC, COD, and aromatic
27 compounds was 84.9%, 69.6%, and 88.7%, respectively.

28
29 The biodegradability of treated landfill leachate improved significantly, exceeding
30 80% in the Zahn-Wellens test, with no detectable leaching of metals from the
31 catalyst. These findings demonstrate the feasibility of repurposing MT as
32 photocatalysts for landfill leachate treatment, offering a sustainable solution to two
33 pressing waste streams.

34

35 Keywords: Sonophotocatalysis; Advanced Oxidation Processes; Biodegradability
36 Enhancement; Zahn-Wellens Test.

37 1. Introduction

38 One of the most important economic activities of Chile is mining (Zhang and
39 Schippers, 2022), where the exportations of copper, gold, and iron are very
40 important. However, this industrial activity generates solid waste known as MT
41 (Malafeevskiy et al., 2025; Campos-Medina et al., 2023), which are a combination
42 of rocks and fluids from concentrators, washeries and mills, resulting from the
43 extraction of metals from the mines (Texeira et al., 2023). In Chile, there are currently
44 765 dams, 22.6% of which are abandoned, for instance, in Andacollo, located in the
45 Coquimbo region, tailing piles are very noticeable. These solid wastes, generated
46 during the production of gold and copper, are an important aspect of the landscape
47 due to their urban locations very close to the inhabitants of this city (Vega et al.,
48 2022); (Leiva G. and Morales, 2013).

49 These MT contain unrecovered and moderately economically relevant amounts of
50 metals (Zhang and Schippers, 2022), considered waste (Marín et al., 2020). The
51 presence of metals in soils poses environmental risks due to their toxicity,
52 accumulation, and persistence (Luo et al., 2012), which may affect the population
53 (Vega et al., 2022). Metals are transported due to the action of erosion by water and
54 wind or acid drainage, negatively affecting the environment (Vega et al., 2022) and
55 disturbing the metabolisms of the microorganisms in the soil where the tailing is (Mao
56 et al., 2024). MT have been found in urban areas, which could impact the population
57 (Moya et al., 2019). Therefore, adequate MT management is transcendental for
58 environmental, economic, social, and other reasons (Botero et al., 2024; Campos-
59 Medina et al., 2023).

60 However, these MT can contain constituents with interesting properties that can be
61 used as catalysts for the advanced oxidation processes, in wastewater treatment,
62 thus supporting a circular economy. The presence of substances such as titanium,
63 iron oxides, copper, and silica, among others, makes them suitable as potential
64 photocatalysts in photo-Fenton and ultrasound processes to treat complex
65 wastewater, such as LL (Poblete et al., 2024a). The use of a catalyst enhances
66 pollutant removal; nevertheless, the load must be optimized since further increments
67 can have a negative effect on the photocatalysis due to the cluster of particles and
68 the decrease in the light pathway (Tekin et al., 2022).

69 LL is generated through the percolation of water from the wet municipal waste and
70 rainfall as it filters through the layers of the landfill, reacting chemically and
71 biologically, obtaining a liquid that presents high amounts of complex and recalcitrant
72 substances, such as dissolved organic matter, chemical oxygen demand (COD),
73 total organic carbon (TOC), heavy metals, phenols, and halogenated compounds
74 (Wdowczyk et al., 2025; Naveen et al., 2017).

75 Applying biological treatments is efficient for young LL because of its biodegradability
76 characteristics. Nevertheless, old and mature LL are not biodegradable due to the
77 presence of toxic compounds, which impede this kind of treatment (Kwarciak-
78 Kozłowska and Fijałkowski, 2021; Seibert et al., 2019). LL is a complex and resistant
79 wastewater with very high concentration of inorganic matter, generated during the

80 decomposition of municipal solid waste in sanitary landfills (Mohammad et al., 2022),
81 being typically characterized by highly concentrated dark color (Jagaba et al., 2021)
82 and elevated levels of dissolved organic matter and salts, along with poor
83 biodegradability (Keyikoglu et al., 2021). In fact, LL is considered much more polluted
84 than the municipal wastes water due to its toxic constituents such as pesticide,
85 phenols and halogenated compounds, nitrogen compounds and organic and
86 inorganic xenobiotics (Kirilova et al., 2025) .

87 Due to their characteristics, old LL are a source of pollution, the landfilling must be
88 secured with an adequate cover system to avoid the infiltration of the LL (Min et al.,
89 2024) and the LL must be adequately treated (Lei et al., 2023; Joshi and Gogate,
90 2019).

91 Conventional treatment systems for LL are based on the use of membrane filtration,
92 ozonation, activated carbon adsorption, and advanced oxidation processes (AOP)
93 (Almeida-Naranjo et al., 2023; Rout et al., 2021). These technologies, especially
94 adsorption, stand out for their simplicity, low cost, and high effectiveness against
95 emerging contaminants (Almeida-Naranjo et al., 2023). Similarly, membrane
96 separation methods such as nanofiltration, ultrafiltration, and reverse osmosis have
97 shown high potential for their removal (Kirilova et al., 2025). AOPs, classified
98 according to their energy source (chemical, UV or electrochemical), enable the
99 efficient degradation, due oxidation, of xenobiotic compounds, with reports of nearly
100 100% removal for drugs such as doxycycline, ciprofloxacin and ibuprofen (Arvaniti
101 et al., 2022).

102 AOPs effectively depurate toxic organic wastewater. For instance, the use of non-
103 thermal plasma, technology applied to generate oxidant radicals to depurate LL that
104 reduces organic matter and metals in this kind of wastewater (Seid-mohammadi et
105 al., 2021).

106 Other of the most interesting alternatives to be applied in LL is the photo-Fenton
107 process (Singa et al., 2023). It is a homogeneous photocatalytic process, where Fe^{2+}
108 ions react with hydrogen peroxide under UV irradiation, generating the powerful
109 oxidant (HO^{\bullet}) and Fe^{3+} ions, and this Fe^{3+} , after that reacts with hydrogen peroxide,
110 generating Fe^{2+} ions and hydroperoxyl, radical (HO_2^{\bullet}), that is a weaker radical
111 (Kösemet et al., 2024).

112 Another important AOP used to oxidise organic contaminants present in water is the
113 interaction between TiO_2 and UV irradiation. When the surface of this semiconductor
114 is irradiated with UV photons, electron-hole pairs are produced, which trigger redox
115 reactions due to the excitation of electrons from the valence band (VB) to the
116 conduction band (CB) (Jari et al., 2025), producing hydroxyl radicals (HO^{\bullet}) and
117 superoxides ($O_2^{\bullet-}$).

118
119 The ultrasound process (US) is also an AOP and an interesting method to produce
120 oxidant radicals in water. One of its key mechanisms is acoustic cavitation in the

121 inertial regime. This phenomenon occurs when high-intensity ultrasound waves
122 propagate through a liquid, causing the formation, growth, and violent collapse of
123 microbubbles. The implosion of these bubbles generates extreme localised
124 conditions- temperatures of thousands of kelvins and pressures of several hundred
125 atmospheres- enabling pyrolytic reactions and the generation of reactive radical
126 species such as hydroxyl radicals (HO•) (Rayaroth et al., 2016). This process offers
127 several advantages, such as improving mass transfer, enhancing turbulence and
128 mixing, and improving catalytic efficiency (Sheik Moideen Thaha and Sathishkumar,
129 2025). Ultrasound irradiation in water generates small cavities with the gases
130 dissolved in the water, which implode, producing conditions of high temperature and
131 pressure, causing a pyrolytic cleavage of water molecules, generating H• and HO•
132 (Su et al., 2024). As can be seen in reactions 1-4, it produced H₂O₂ and HO₂• under
133 US irradiation:

139))) represents ultrasound irradiation.

140 Also, the abrupt collapse of the bubble due to US irradiation emits picosecond
141 flashes of UV irradiation (Hiller et al., 1994), called bubble sonoluminescence, that
142 can be taken advantage of for the degradation of organic pollutants (Gareev et al.,
143 2023), via direct photolysis or photo-Fenton process, because it can be produced in
144 the bulk of the polluted water, minimizing the scattering effect caused by colloids or
145 turbidity in the water, very relevant in LL, even after filtration and
146 coagulation/flocculation processes (Alanís et al., 2025).

147 Another potential application of the US process is in combating *Helicobacter pylori*.
148 Following ultrasound exposure, singlet oxygen is generated, which contributes to
149 bacterial elimination by disrupting biofilms and enhancing the removal of intracellular
150 bacteria through the stimulation of autophagy (Yin et al., 2025).

151 US can also be used in welding processes, for example, Ultrasonic spot welding of
152 copper foils (O–Cu) was improved by using a surface gradient structure, which
153 generated a nanocrystalline layer with lower friction. This increased mechanical
154 strength and welding temperature and modified the fracture mechanism, replacing
155 cleavage with micro-pits (Ni et al., 2025).

156 Although advanced oxidation processes such as photo-Fenton and US are widely
157 used to treat complex wastewaters, challenges such as high operational costs,
158 limited catalyst efficiency, and the need for high energy inputs remain. Despite the
159 environmental risks posed by MT, no study has investigated their catalytic potential

160 in wastewater treatment, making this work the first to explore this approach. Our
161 study proposes an innovative approach to address both environmental concerns
162 associated with MT and treating persistent organic pollutants in LL.

163 Circular economy strategies promote the use of waste as an input to generate value
164 a second time or several times and extract valuable substances as metals (Nesterov
165 et al., 2024). For instance, wastes as MT are a source of rare earth elements that
166 can be incorporated in economic processes (Lima et al., 2022). In this context,
167 approaching MT from a circular economy perspective represents a significant
168 opportunity to reduce environmental impacts and increase the value of materials
169 generated during extraction and processing operations (Tayebi-Khorami et al.,
170 2019). The revalorisation of MT may promote the circular economy and waste
171 reduction by transforming these materials from hazardous waste into valuable
172 resources for environmental remediation.

173 Therefore, this study contributes to the dual goals of reducing environmental
174 pollution and enhancing resource efficiency in the mining industry by performing a
175 factorial design to determine the importance of the factors evaluated.

176 Considering that, in the best-known of the authors, there are no published studies
177 that have used MT as a catalyst to depurate wastewater, this is the first study aimed
178 at applying MT as a photocatalyst to evaluate this in the treatment of landfill leachate,
179 performing a factorial design to determine the importance of the factors evaluated.

180 Unlike previous studies that have used modified industrial materials or commercial
181 catalysts such as TiO_2 , our work explores the direct use of mining tailings without
182 prior structural modification as active catalysts in a sonophotocatalytic process to
183 treat mature landfill leachates.

184 Given that MT contain minerals with adsorbent and catalytic properties, the
185 hypothesis of this study is that these can be used as effective catalysts in
186 sonophotocatalytic processes to increase the degradation of organic pollutants and
187 the biodegradability of mature landfill leachates, without causing metal leaching. This
188 study evaluates, for the first time, this application of the MT under a factorial design
189 that considers catalyst load, H_2O_2 concentration and pH as critical factors.

190 Therefore, an ultrasound process coupled with a photocatalytic process, with
191 different loads of MT, concentrations of H_2O_2 , and pH of the solution, was applied to
192 study the removal of pollutants present in a LL.

193 2.- Materials and methods

194 2.1- Sample Collection

195 50 kg of MT was obtained from Andacollo City, (30° 14' 14" S, 71° 5' 1.79" W), Chile,
196 where the tailing is very near the population, as can be seen in the photographs
197 presented in Figure 1. The sample was taken to the Universidad Católica del Norte
198 and stored in a closed container in the dark, before characterisation and
199 experimentation.

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Fig. 1. Photographs of the MT obtained from Andacollo.

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2.2.- Catalyst Characterization

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The characterisation of the MT was performed using X-ray diffraction (XRD) and quantitative evaluation of minerals by scanning electron microscopy (QEMSCAN), and the equipment was an X-ray Diffractometer Bruker model D8 Advance and goniometer Vertical Bragg-Brentano radiation Cu Ka1 ($\lambda = 1,5406 \text{ \AA}$).

207 The MT was mainly composed of Feldspars (Plagioclase Series), Quartz (SiO₂),
 208 Biotite/Phlogopite, Muscovite/Sericite, Cu-bearing Phyllosilicates, Montmorillonite,
 209 and TiO₂ rutile phase, with a mass percentage composition of 36.43, 15.61, 7.57,
 210 7.40, 5.58, 3.38, and 0.39, respectively. Figure 2 shows the X-ray diffraction (XRD)
 211 and quantitative evaluation of minerals by scanning electron microscopy
 212 (QEMSCAN).

215 Fig. 2. Characterization of the MT by a) X-ray diffraction (XRD) and b)
 216 quantitative evaluation of minerals by scanning electron microscopy (QEMSCAN).

217 The specific surface area of MT was measured according Brunauer–Emmett–Teller
 218 isothermal analysis (BET) using a Nova 600 from Anton Paar (Austria) equipment
 219 obtaining a value of 122 m²/g, with an error of 2%.

220

221 The LL was sampled from the authorized landfill in Coquimbo called El Panul (29°
222 59' 56" S, 71° 23' 21" W, Chile), where the domestic solid wastes of Coquimbo, Chile,
223 are disposed of. The main characteristics of LL are detailed in Table 1.

224 Table 1. Raw landfill leachate characteristics.

Parameter	Value	Standard deviations
TOC (mg/L)	4192.6	402
COD (mg/L)	8350.4	498.2
pH	8.9	0.3
Total solids (mg/L)	20,100	350
Total Iron (mg/L)	41.600	260
Abs ₂₅₄	0.4	0.03
Faecal coliforms (mpn)	0	0
Chloride (mg/L)	6230.4	550.3

225 mpn: most probable number

226 2.3.- Landfill Leachate Treatments

227 To improve the performance of the sonophotocatalytic process, which is negatively
228 affected by the shadow effect, the leachate was pretreated by
229 coagulation/flocculation with 1000 mg/L of FeCl₃, following the methodology of
230 Poblete and Painemal, (2018). The mixture was stirred at 150 rpm, allowed to settle
231 for 6 hours, and then filtered through a 5 µm filter.

232 To enhance the performance of the sonophotocatalytic process, which is negatively
233 affected by the shadow effect, the LL was pre-treated using the
234 coagulation/flocculation process to remove suspended solids. This pretreatment
235 consisted of adding 1000 mg/L of coagulant to the LL, which was FeCl₃ (≥99% of
236 purity, Merck), and stirring the mixture at 150 rpm, according to the methodology
237 published by our research group (Poblete and Painemal, 2018). After that, the LL
238 was left to stand for 6 hours to recover the supernatant, which was then submitted
239 to a filtration process with a 5 µm-pore size filter.

240 The pretreated LL was placed in a sonophotoreactor, which is a cylindrical container
241 with a volume of 1000 mL, and the LL was submerged in a probe from the US system
242 (Sonic-generator VCX-500), which generates an ultrasonic wave of 20 kHz and 500
243 W of power. Additionally, the LL was submerged in a UVc lamp that emits at 254 nm,
244 with 40 W of power (see Figure 3). In all the runs, to protect the US probe, the
245 temperature of the sonophotoreactor was set to 20 °C using a cooling jacket, which
246 was controlled using a chiller of 250 W. The solution was stirred using a magnetic
247 stirrer set at 500 rpm.

Fig. 3. Picture of the sonophotoreactor.

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250 The ultrasonic experiments were conducted at 100% power capacity of the
 251 equipment, and the pulse and silent times were set to change continuously from 0
 252 to 10,000 ms. The factorial design experiment lasted 60 min for each run, and all
 253 runs were performed in triplicate.

254 2.4.- Factorial Design

255 Taking into consideration that it is the first study focused on the use of MT as a
 256 catalyst in the US and photocatalytic process, it was necessary to establish the
 257 importance of factors, such as the catalyst load, the concentration of H₂O₂ and the
 258 pH of the solution, as well as to determine the range of these factors that maximise
 259 the removal of organic pollutants the LL.

260 Consequently, a two-level full factorial design with centre points was carried out,
 261 where the factors were: catalyst load (factor A, with levels of 200, 1000 and 2000
 262 mg/L), concentration of H₂O₂ (factor B, with levels of 1000, 2000 and 3000 mg/L)
 263 and pH of the solution (factor C, with levels of 3, 6 and 8.9), as can be seen in Table
 264 2. These levels were selected considering previous results using an industrial solid
 265 waste as a catalyst (Poblete et al., 2011; Poblete et al., 2024b). MT was added to
 266 the sonophotoreactor in its original form, i.e., as a powder.

267 Table 2. Factorial experimental design for sonophotocatalytic experiments

	[Catalyst] (level)	[H ₂ O ₂] (level)	pH (level)
1	200 mg/L (-1)	1000 mg/L (-1)	8.9 (1)

2	200 mg/L	(-1)	1000 mg/L	(-1)	3	(-1)
3	200 mg/L	(-1)	3000 mg/L	(1)	8.9	(1)
4	2000 mg/L	(1)	1000 mg/L	(-1)	3	(-1)
5	2000 mg/L	(1)	3000 mg/L	(1)	8.9	(1)
6	2000 mg/L	(1)	1000 mg/L	(-1)	8.9	(1)
7	1000 mg/L	(0)	2000 mg/L	(0)	6	(0)
8	2000 mg/L	(1)	3000 mg/L	(1)	3	(-1)
9	200 mg/L	(-1)	3000 mg/L	(1)	3	(-1)

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269 The response of the factorial design was evaluated according to the removal of TOC
270 and aromatic compounds (Abs₂₅₄). Data were analysed using the software program
271 Minitab 19.

272 The factorial design with runs of 60 min duration was carried out as a first approach
273 focused on the use of MT as a catalyst in the sonophotocatalytic process, and since
274 all experiments lasted the same amount of time, the results can be used to compare
275 the effect of the factors and to identify which comparison of levels optimizes the
276 outcome, in order to subsequently carry out a long-term experiment with the
277 optimized conditions. Therefore, the optimal factor levels for TOC and aromatic
278 compound removal were applied in a 3-hour experiment of a sonophotocatalytic
279 process, to evaluate the removal of pollutants from LL and the change in its
280 biodegradability throughout the treatment, using the Zahn-Wellens test, because
281 Zahn-Wellens bioassay is more proper for biodegradability evaluations over time (da
282 Costa et al., 2018) and is adequate to provide valuable information referred to the
283 biodegradability improvement and establish the optimal point to stop the chemical
284 process and combine to a biological treatment considering the environmental
285 requirements for discharge (Welter et al., 2018).

286 For all the runs, the MT used in the reactor was dried at 105 °C for two hours and
287 particle sizes selected were in the range of 75-150 µm (Poblete et al., 2011).

288

289 2.5.- Analytical Determination and Equipment

290 To measure the concentration of TOC in the LL, 50 µL of samples were injected into
291 a Shimadzu TOC-L (Japan), at 650 °C combustion, through acid-catalysed, using a
292 non-dispersive infrared (NDIR) detector. Shimadzu provided all devices and
293 reagents used for TOC measurements. The aromatic compounds (Abs₂₅₄) present
294 in LL were measured using a UV/VIS spectrophotometer at 254 nm (Liu et al., 2015)
295 (Optizen Pop Series UV/VIS, Mecasys, Korea). Chemical oxygen demand of LL was
296 determined through the colourimetric technique (EPA 410.4 protocol), using a
297 spectrophotometer Hanna HI83099 (Hanna Instruments, USA). Total copper
298 present in LL was established according to the Bicinchoninate Acid Method (HI-
299 93702-01). The Iron and aluminium (EPA phenanthroline 315B and HI93712-01
300 methods, respectively) with the Hanna HI83099 spectrophotometer.

301 The concentration of H₂O₂ in the solution was measured according to the iodometric
302 method (at 350 nm) (Kormann et al., 1988), using the Hanna HI83099
303 spectrophotometer.

304 To evaluate the change in the biodegradability of the LL due to the
305 sonophotocatalytic process, the Zahn-Wellens test was carried out, according to the
306 OECD, Directive 88/303/EEC protocol (OECD, 1992).

307 The test lasts 28 days in an open vessel, where the evaluated water is adjusted to
308 pH≈7, and the mixture is continuously stirred at 500 rpm and kept at room
309 temperature. The biological solutions are constituted by previously centrifuged
310 activated sludge that was obtained from an urban wastewater treatment plant
311 located in Tongoy (lat 30°15'27"S, long 71°29'33"W), Coquimbo, and mineral
312 nutrients (K₂HPO₄, KH₂PO₄, NH₄Cl, Na₂HPO₄, MgSO₄, CaCl₂, and FeCl₃).

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314 The blank and control runs were carried out using distilled water and glucose,
315 respectively. The biodegradation (%) was calculated according to the following
316 equation:

317

$$318 \quad D_t = 1 - \frac{(C_t - C_B)}{(C_A - C_{BA})} \quad (5)$$

319

320 where D_t is the percentage of biodegradation, C_t and C_B were the TOC of the mixture
321 concentration (mg/L) in the mixture and in the blank, respectively, measured at a t
322 time; C_a and C_{BA} were the TOC of the mixture and in the blank, respectively,
323 measured 3 h after the beginning of the run. The treated LL is considered
324 biodegradable when biodegradation is higher than 70%.

325 Also, an Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) Analysis of
326 Water was carried out in the presence of the MT mass and at the pH conditions that
327 improved the pollutant removal in the factorial design, under US irradiation. For this
328 purpose, the water samples were filtered at 0.22 μm and analysed using a Thermo
329 Fisher iCAP TQe ICP-MS-TQ in S-SQ-iKED mode. The detection limit of the
330 measurement is 100 ng/L.

331

332 3. Results and Discussion

333 3.1.- Factorial design

334 Figure 4 shows the effect estimates of the degradation of pollutants due to the
335 evaluated factors, where it is possible to observe that factor C (pH of the solution) is
336 the most crucial parameter in the removal of TOC and aromatic compounds from the
337 LL. This relevant impact on the oxidation process can be because of pH on the
338 solubilization of iron and copper in the LL, which enhances the presence of this
339 catalyst in photo-Fenton and photo-Fenton-like processes, respectively (Zong et al.,
340 2025; Bhaskar et al., 2025).

341 The normal effects plot has irregular intervals on the Y-axis because it uses a scale
342 based on the quantiles of the standard normal distribution. This representation

343 allows you to visually identify significant effects that deviate from the straight line
 344 expected under the null hypothesis.

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346 Figure 4. Probability versus effect estimates for a) TOC and b) Aromatic
 347 compounds removal (%).
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The Pareto chart, depicted in Figure 5, presents the influence of the evaluated factor, where the results agree with those shown in Figure 4, where the pH is the most relevant factor on the effect of removal of TOC and aromatic compounds from the LL, showing a significant difference. The reason lies in the crucial impact of the solution pH on the sonophotocatalytic process (Kallawar et al., 2024).

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Figure 5. Pareto chart of effects for TOC and Aromatic compounds removal (%). Factors: A ([catalyst]), B ([H₂O₂]) and C (pH). α represents Statistical significance level and PSE length represents Pseudo Standard Error. p-value=0.05.

The levels of the factors that maximise the removal of TOC and aromatic compounds are a higher load of catalyst, a higher concentration of H₂O₂ and lower pH (see Fig. 6). Under the optimised conditions, it was possible to get a removal of 29.8 and 50.2% of TOC and aromatic compounds, respectively. Also, the removal was very low at lower load of catalyst, lower concentration of H₂O₂, and higher pH (5 % for TOC and 2% for aromatic compounds). The results obtained in the optimized

367 condition are in agreement with those obtained in previous research of our
 368 investigation group, which achieved a removal of 50.2% of aromatic compounds
 369 using an industrial fly ash as catalyst, 576 kHz of US frequency and a solution of LL
 370 adjusted at pH to 3 (Poblete et al., 2024). Also, these results are lower than those
 371 obtained in a research that used 950 mg/L of TiO₂ as photocatalyst and a UVc lamp
 372 to depurate a LL, presenting a TOC removal of 72.8% and the difference can be due
 373 to the power of the UVc lamp, which was 400 W (Aibuedefe and Tina, 2024), much
 374 higher than that used in this research.
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376
 377 Figure 6. Mean a) TOC and b) Aromatic compounds removal (%).
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379 The better results obtained using a higher load of MT can be explained by
 380 considering that a high load of catalyst enhances the area accessible for the
 381 adsorption process and the production of oxidant radicals, causing an improvement
 382 in the degradation (Srisangari and Marathe, 2024). Nevertheless, when the optimum
 383 catalyst load is exceeded, the solution becomes turbid, increasing the turbidity of
 384 water by reducing the efficiency of UV radiation in the aqueous medium (Gao et al.,
 385 2022).

386 Also, Figure 6 shows that the removal of aromatic compounds of the LL was
 387 enhanced when a higher concentration of H₂O₂ was added to the solution, and this
 388 can be because this reagent, in the presence of US cavitation, improves the
 389 production of hydroxyl radicals (Wang and Wang, 2020).

390 In addition, when exposed to UV-C irradiation, the photolysis of H₂O₂ is induced,
 391 producing more hydroxyl radicals, as illustrated in the following equation:

393 Therefore, a high concentration of H₂O₂, enhances the degradation of pollutants;
 394 however, when the presence of this reagent is higher than the optimal, a scavenger
 395 of HO[•] can be formed due to recombination, generating hydroxyperoxyl radical,

396 which have lower oxidant potential than hydroxyl radicals (Merdoud et al., 2024;
397 Innocenzi et al., 2019).

398 Also, as can be seen in Figure 6, the removal of pollutants is higher when the level
399 of the factor pH is lower, at pH=3. This is due to the low recombination of HO[•] under
400 acidic conditions, enhancing the degradation of organic compounds (Thomas et al.,
401 2020). Considering the effect of pH on the US process, the pollutants accumulate in
402 the gas-liquid interface of the bubble being attacked for HO[•] in acid conditions
403 (Ghosh and Sahu, 2024). It is necessary to consider that the oxidation of organic
404 compounds happens in both the interfacial film and gaseous zone due to pyrolysis
405 and the hydroxyl radicals at lower pH. Additionally, in acid conditions, there is an
406 electrostatic attraction between the oppositely hydrophobic molecules and the gas-
407 liquid interface, enhancing the degradation of pollutants (Pirsaheb and Moradi,
408 2020).

409 The use of the US process in photocatalytic treatment provokes local turbulence in
410 the liquid, enhancing the mass transfer and increasing the availability of the reaction
411 sites, while also promoting the dispersion of the MT particles, increasing their
412 interaction with the pollutants (Ahmed and Mohamed, 2024). US cavitation
413 generates high-frequency pressure waves that cause compression and expansion
414 cycles, creating microjets with high pressure and temperature effects. This
415 phenomenon destabilizes particles and promotes the dispersion of agglomerates
416 due to intense shear forces, which increases the effective contact area between
417 particles and improves process efficiency (Li et al., 2025)

418
419 As was described before, MT was mainly constituted of Feldspars (plagioclase
420 Series), Quartz (SiO₂), Biotite/Phlogopite, Muscovite/Sericite, Cu-bearing
421 Phyllosilicates, Montmorillonite, and TiO₂ rutile phase. Feldspars are crystalline with
422 amorphous fractions of aluminosilicate and are considered adsorbent materials,
423 where stability ensures that the sorptivity capacity is enhanced at elevated
424 temperature (Youssef et al., 2021), including the plagioclase series (Aghabeyk et al.,
425 2022). In the case of Biotite/Phlogopite, under UV irradiation, its substance with a
426 narrower band gap energy can be excited, producing h⁺/e⁻ pairs, promoting several
427 reactions of oxidation (Mohamed, 2024). Muscovite is a layered silicate mineral
428 (Chen et al., 2022), considered an adsorbent material and a heterogeneous catalyst,
429 which can be used in wastewater treatment (Aboussabek et al., 2024), similar to
430 natural inorganic diatomite, in terms of its adsorbent properties (Bai et al., 2024b).

431 Cu-bearing Phyllosilicate is a clay with an interesting capacity for the adsorption of
432 organic pollutants present in water (Mamine et al., 2024). This mineral is constituted
433 by atoms of oxygen and silicon, as a silica layer, and by aluminium atoms (alumina
434 or aluminium hydroxide layer), and can be applied in wastewater treatment as an
435 adsorbent material (Sanavada et al., 2023). In the MT, montmorillonite was also
436 found, which is a clay that presents interesting adsorption capacity with a high
437 surface area (Naing et al., 2022), where rapidity was demonstrated for wastewater
438 treatment (Cao et al., 2025). Besides, it was established that montmorillonite
439 stimulates the formation of OH[•] due to its presence of Fe, and when hydrogen

440 peroxide is added to the solution, under ultrasonic waves or UV irradiation (Demirtas
441 et al., 2025). TiO₂ is a semiconductor under UV irradiation, which has shown a high
442 photocatalytic ability, presenting chemical stability and biodegradability (Talukdar et
443 al., 2020).

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445 3.2.- Long-term experiments

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447 Figure 7 shows the variation in the concentration of COD, TOC and aromatic
448 compounds of pretreated LL as a function of treatment time, subjected to a
449 sonocatalytic process under the conditions that optimise pollutant removal: 2000
450 mg/L of catalyst (MT), 3000 mg/L of H₂O₂, and a solution adjusted to pH 3. As the
451 treatment time increases, a progressive reduction in all three parameters is
452 observed, indicating a sustained degradation of organic pollutants over time. After 3
453 h of treatment, the removal of TOC, COD, and aromatic compounds were 84.9%,
454 69.6%, and 88.7%, respectively.

455 As can be seen, the results obtained in these runs are better than the obtained in the
456 factorial design, that lasted 60 minutes each, where the higher removal of TOC was
457 29.8%, and is due to the longer duration of this experiment, 180 mins, allowing a
458 highest oxidation of organic matter (Mukhtiar et al., 2025; Rostami et al., 2025).

459 These results are similar to those obtained using the sono-photo-Fenton process, in
460 the treatment of a LL, achieving a removal of COD and aromatic compounds of 93%
461 and 77%, respectively (Bellouk et al., 2023), using the traditional reagents of the
462 photo-Fenton process, showing that these processes are very competitive in
463 comparison with other AOPs, according to the phytotoxicity evaluation. These high
464 results of the removal of pollutants can be due to the interaction of the different
465 constituents of the MT, due to its photocatalytic and adsorbent properties.

466 Also, the results obtained in this research are higher than those reported in a study
467 where the treatment of LL was evaluated using the commercial TiO₂ of Degussa as
468 catalysis and, after 3 h. of irradiation with a UVc lamp, a TOC removal of 76% was
469 achieved (Becerra et al., 2020). The difference between both processes may be
470 attributed to the fact that, in the case of the present study, a sonophotocatalytic
471 process was applied.

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Figure 7. Change in the concentration of COD, TOC, and aromatic compounds of LL, submitted to a sonocatalytic process using 2000 mg/L of MT as catalyst, 3000 mg/L of H₂O₂, and solution at pH 3.

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3.3.- Blank experiments

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Considering MT's capacity as a photocatalytic and adsorbent material and the participation of the US process, to elucidate the effect of the involved processes in the removal of pollutants from LL, blank experiments were conducted for photocatalysis, ultrasound, and adsorption (in the dark), all three using 2000 mg/L MT, at pH=3, for 3 h of run. In the case of the adsorption process, it was conducted separately in the dark, without UV irradiation and without ultrasound.

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Figure 8. Change in the concentration of TOC of LL, submitted to photocatalysis, ultrasound and adsorption (dark) process, using 2000 mg/L of MT as catalyst, 3000 mg/L of H₂O₂ and solution at pH 3.

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Figure 8 shows that the photocatalytic process, using MT as a catalyst, offers the highest removal of pollutants, followed by the US process, while the lowest performance was obtained by the adsorption process, with TOC removals of 63.1%, 58.9%, and 40.6%, respectively. These results show that the main process that has an effect on oxidation was the photocatalytic process, possibly due to the presence and interaction of Biotite/Phlogopite, montmorillonite and TiO₂, which under UV irradiation and H₂O₂ can produce a significant amount of hydroxyl radicals, triggering a series of oxidation reactions (Mohamed, 2024; Aboussabek et al., 2024; Demirtas et al., 2025; Talukdar et al., 2020).

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3.4.- Assessment of biodegradability

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As can be observed in the results obtained in this research, a high removal of the evaluated organic pollutant in treating LL using MT was achieved. However, it can be inferred that using solid mining waste can be dangerous or complex, considering the presence of heavy metals that can be leached in solution (Bai et al., 2022), that can be leached under acid conditions (Bai et al., 2024a) and interact with the constituents of the matrix. Therefore, the change of concentration of iron, copper, and aluminium was measured before and after the sonophotocatalytic process, using 2000 mg/L MT, at pH=3, for 3 h of run. No increase was observed in the concentration of iron, copper, and aluminium in the LL submitted to this process.

513 The results of the biodegradability assay carried out on the LL submitted to the
 514 pretreatment (coagulation/flocculation process) and on the LL submitted to
 515 sonophotocatalysis (also pretreated) are depicted in Fig. 9. The control (distilled
 516 water and glucose) and the LL submitted to a sonophotocatalysed treatment. The
 517 LL had an initial concentration of 705.3 mg/L of TOC, and after the bioassay present
 518 a TOC degradation higher than 70%, validating the test. Also, it can be seen that the
 519 oxidation processes achieved greater TOC removal than the control, obtaining
 520 83.2% and 75.0%, respectively. In the case of the raw LL and the submitted to the
 521 pretreatment, the removal of TOC was 7.2 and 45.9%, respectively, after 28 days of
 522 assay. The very low biodegradability of the raw LL obtained is consistent with the
 523 results obtained (de Pauli et al., 2018), who obtained a biodegradability of the raw
 524 LL of 10%.

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526 Figure 9. Biodegradability by Zahn-Wellen assay for control, pre-treated LL and
 527 sonophotocatalyzed LL.
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529 After 28 days of bioassay, these results can be attributed to the transformation of
 530 organic substances into sub-products with lower toxic substances (de Pauli et al.,
 531 2018) such as fulvic acids present in the LL (Gomes et al., 2021) chlorinated aliphatic
 532 compounds, surfactants, organic dyes and aromatic compounds into less complex
 533 forms, which increases the biodegradability and reduces their toxicity (Gałwa-
 534 Widera, 2025).

535 In Figure 9, the results of the Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-
 536 MS) Analysis of water at pH 3 and in the presence of 2 mg/L of MT are presented.

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539 Figure 10. Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry Analysis of Water in the
540 Presence of MT

541 The results show the presence of Ti, Si, Cu, Fe, K, Al, Li and Cl. However, as can
542 be seen in the biodegradability analysis, these concentrations are not hazardous to
543 the leachate.

544 3.5.- Circular Economy aspects

545 This research demonstrates the efficiency of using MT as catalysts in the treatment
546 of LL. Additionally, it contributes to the circular economy approach, as it enables the
547 revaluation of mining waste that has historically been considered an environmental
548 liability. From a circularity perspective, the MT used experimentally can be used
549 directly as a functional raw material in a wastewater treatment process. Considering
550 a load of 2000 mg/L of MT to treat leachate, which has very high volumes in a landfill,
551 and in the case of El Panul, where the LL studied was sampled, has a total volume
552 of 280 m³, the process would require a quantity of 560 tons of MT. Although no life
553 cycle assessment was conducted, the direct reuse of MT, without requiring intensive
554 energy for structural modification, constitutes an advance in the design of
555 environmentally sustainable processes. In addition, it was verified that there is no
556 leaching of heavy metals (Fe, Cu, Al) during the process, providing key evidence on
557 the environmental safety of the circular use of hazardous waste.

558 Another relevant study focused in the used of waste as precursor of catalyst was
559 published by Yang et al., (2025) who evaluated the performance of a material,
560 prepared with Fe-Ni monometallic and bimetallic catalysts, from rice husks, showing
561 a high synergy between Fe and Ni and reduced the possibility of active site
562 deactivation.

563 4.- Conclusions

564 This study demonstrates the feasibility of reusing MT as a heterogeneous catalyst in
565 the sonophotocatalytic treatment of mature landfill leachate. The MT, primarily
566 composed of feldspars, phyllosilicates, montmorillonite, and rutile TiO₂, exhibited
567 both photocatalytic and adsorptive properties that contributed to the effective
568 degradation of organic pollutants.

569 A full factorial design identified pH as the most influential parameter, with the highest
570 removal efficiencies observed at acidic conditions (pH 3), high catalyst loading (2000
571 mg/L), and elevated hydrogen peroxide concentration (3000 mg/L). Under optimized
572 conditions, TOC, COD, and aromatic compounds were removed by 84.9%, 69.6%,
573 and 88.7%, respectively, within 3 hours of treatment.

574 The sonophotocatalytic process also significantly enhanced the biodegradability of
575 LL, as evidenced by the Zahn-Wellens test, with post-treatment values exceeding
576 the 70% threshold for biodegradability. Importantly, no leaching of potentially toxic
577 metals (Fe, Cu, Al) from the MT was observed under the applied conditions,
578 supporting the environmental safety of this approach.

579 These findings provide a novel alternative for the valorisation of MT, contributing to
580 circular economy strategies in the mining and waste management sectors. Future
581 research should focus on long-term stability, catalyst reusability, and the scale-up of
582 the treatment process to validate its applicability at an industrial level.

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587 Regional 2008 EQU 25 Conicyt 2009-2010.

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